

AN ETHICS-IN-ACTION FRAMEWORK FOR DESIGNING DATA-DRIVEN PRODUCT SERVICE SYSTEMS

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PHD PROJECT SUMMARY

The rising interest in tech ethics, design ethics and AI ethics in both industry and academia highlight the need for deeper engagement with the moral dimensions of current design practice, particularly around data-driven systems. Following a surge of criticism on traditional consequentialist, and value- or principle-based suggestions (Mittelstadt, 2019; Munn, 2022; Green, 2021; Birhane, 2021; Bareis & Katzenbach, 2022; Baum, 2020), recent research has turned towards relational ethics as a promising alternative to explore the messy, complex and fluid characteristics of moral considerations in technical systems (Frauenberger et al., 2017; DiSalvo, 2022). This project follows these approaches, seeking to prototype new methods of ethics-in-action for design practices of data driven technologies, starting from a point of productive uncertainty and openness for tension, which positions ethics as a contextual, situated doing, inherently embedded in the practice of designing. I use the lens of sociotechnical imaginaries (Jasanoff, 2015) as a means of investigating suggested futures and their normative and moral commitments. The imaginaries which designers and engineers hold about the futures within which their products or services operate, become mundane frames of world-making, manifesting what designers position as ethically desirable (Ames, 2019; Bareis & Katzenbach, 2022; Blythe et al., 2018; Dahlgren et al., 2021).

Through the combination of sociotechnical imaginaries and relational ethics I seek to develop a conceptual framework that enables designers to engage with the ethical dimensions of their work productively and intentionally in practice, while leaving space for the softer parts of *doing ethics*.

The project is framed around two research questions:

RQ 1: What productive sociotechnical imaginaries are currently in place in design practice, and do they limit the kind of ethics that designers see as possible?

RQ 2: How can we work with, expand, or redirect these imaginaries to include a relational ethic and how can this shift of imaginaries affect practice in productive ways?

RELATION TO NORDES DESIGN COMMUNITY

The topic of this year's Nordes Conference is very much in line with my research interests and fields of study. My project would very much benefit from feedback and input from other attending ESRs and faculty, who I expect to have further interesting insights and advice on doing research within this complex and fluid field of designing for the in between and the emerging world making resulting from it. I consider the consortium a valuable learning experience that can help me shape the long-term vision and direction for my research. I hope to contribute to the general consortium as well as my peers' research by bringing in diverse insights and lessons from my studies of prototyping speculative design experiments in industry contexts. At the time of the Nordes Consortium, I will be two years into my PhD, and thus nearing my final year due to the three-year structure of Danish PhDs. This will be the only Nordes Doctoral Consortium that I would be able to attend, and it would be a great opportunity to share my work and receive feedback, guidance, and input from peers outside of my current research network.

SHORT- AND LONG-TERM GOALS

By the time of the Nordes Consortium, I will have finished the main part of my data collection. In my final year, I aim to distil the learnings from the three studies into an alternative suggestion for how to approach ethics as a doing.

My long-term goals are to continue to broaden and deepen the conversation around ethics in technology through applied practice beyond academia. I have entered this PhD program following an entrepreneurial background, as co-founder and Head of Design of a technology and design studio, and therefore want to contribute towards bridging the gap between academic research and industry needs further on.

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